

THE ROLE OF MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF GOODS

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Abstract. *In this article, the influence of modern information and communication technologies on social and economic development is extremely high, which, first of all, increases labor productivity, ensures competitiveness, creates new goods, and reduces production and service costs.*

Keywords: *information, communication, technology, labor, goods, service, experience, innovation.*

РОЛЬ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ И КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ТОВАРОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье чрезвычайно велико влияние современных информационных и коммуникационных технологий на социально-экономическое развитие, что, прежде всего, повышает производительность труда, обеспечивает конкурентоспособность, создает новые товары, снижает затраты на производство и обслуживание.*

Ключевые слова: *информация, связь, технология, труд, товар, услуга, опыт, инновация.*

INTRODUCTION

World experience shows that the role and importance of information and communication technologies (ICT), which includes the production of computer and telecommunication technologies, software products and the provision of a wide range of interactive services based on them, is growing in the global economy.

At the same time, the turnover of goods sold by business entities through the use of electronic commerce is considered retail, regardless of their size. It is also decided to attract international consulting companies and experts in the field of ICT, to develop its own IT infrastructure and to strengthen the material and technical base, as well as to be implemented at the expense of the funds of the ICT Development Fund.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 355 of December 31, 2013 "On measures to introduce a system for assessing the state of development of information and communication technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan", starting from the first quarter of 2014, Information Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan and The state of implementation and development of ICT in state and economic management, local government bodies is analyzed every quarter by the experts of the "Electronic Government" system development center and the Information and Public Security Center of the Ministry of Communications Development, and rating evaluation works are being carried out. Using information and communication technologies, interactive public services are aimed at the great

goal of raising human interests to the highest level of value, and on this basis, it is intended to make people's distance closer and their problems easier. As a result of the reforms carried out in this regard, it can be mentioned that 197 types of services have been registered from the register of statistical data, and the number of services provided by state bodies through websites has reached 617. The impact of modern information and communication technologies on social and economic development is extremely high, which is manifested, first of all, in the increase of labor productivity, competitiveness, creation of new jobs, and reduction of production and service costs. Ultimately, the export potential of the country will increase, the opportunity to enter foreign markets and open new trade routes will expand. In this regard, the task of modern information and communication technologies is primarily to determine a high-quality, reliable and competitive product, its market place and customer demand. Simply put, modern information and communication technologies act as mediators in this process. Mediation, on the other hand, is an activity that creates an opportunity to conclude a deal that is beneficial for both parties, that is, the producer and the consumer. It can be seen that the duration and continuity of the activity of the intermediary depends on the quality, competitiveness and guarantee of the product offered to the consumer, in a word, the brand. A brand is the image of a product or service in the consumer's imagination, which is manifested as the trust gained by the company offering this service or product, its mental or spiritual value in front of the consumer. In general, a brand is the image, value and reputation of a company, product or service.

The tasks of the rating assessment are to analyze the current state of ICT introduction in organizations, to identify obstacles, to eliminate them and to provide practical assistance in the development of a plan of measures aimed at increasing the efficiency of activities, and then to prepare priority proposals for the introduction and development of ICT.

RESULTS

The impact of modern ICT on socio-economic development is extremely high, and is first of all manifested in the increase of labor productivity, competitiveness, creation of new jobs, reduction of production and service costs. "Internet markets", i.e. World Wide Web (WWW) Internet trade networks, are rapidly developing as a non-traditional business in the effective organization of e-commerce activities of companies.

The development of ICT led to the emergence of electronic commerce, the most important system of the Internet. The concept of modern marketing became the basis for the emergence of a new direction of Internet marketing¹²⁸.

DISCUSSION

One of the main characteristics of Internet marketing is its hypermedia nature, which is characterized by high efficiency in the presentation and absorption of information, significantly increasing marketing opportunities in improving relations between businesses and consumers. The role of the Internet is not limited to communicative functions, but also includes the ability to conclude transactions, make purchases and make payments, which provides the characteristics of a global electronic market. Electronic commerce (e-Commerce) tools are widely used in the practice of developed countries to organize effective sales of products produced by enterprises. These four models of e-commerce, C2C, B2B, B2C and C2B, are common in developed countries.

Effective use of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) in marketing activities leads to effective formation of marketing technologies of enterprises, and in turn,

traditional and outdated marketing technologies are increasingly pushed out of practice. Expanding the possibilities of using marketing technologies such as neuromarketing, cognitive marketing, sensor marketing, mobile marketing, internet marketing and crowdsourcing methods in industrial enterprises allows them to operate effectively and ensure their competitiveness.

CONCLUSIONS

Internet technology has allowed entrepreneurs with new ideas to enter the industry, making it easier for customers to find, evaluate and buy the goods they need. These models are compatible with the long-term revolution in consumer product markets, resulting in the effective transfer of market judgment from the manufacturer to the retailer.

REFERENCES

1. Decision PQ-1730 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further introduction and development of modern information and communication technologies". National database of legal documents, 01.12.2017, No. 07/17/3415/0345.
2. Decree No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". // People's word, February 8, 2017, issue 28 (6722).
3. Kevin Lane Keller (1993) "Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer-Based Brand Equity," *Journal of Marketing*, 57 (January), 1 -22.
4. Lassar W., Mittal B. and Sharma A. (1995) "Measuring Customer-Based Brand Equity", *Journal of Consumer Marketing* 12(4): 11-19.
5. Park CS and Srinivasan V. (1994) "A survey-based method for measuring and understanding brand equity and its extendibility", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 31, May, pp. 271 - 884.
6. Kamakura WA and Russell GJ (1991) "Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Brand Quality with Scanner Data: Implications for Brand Equity", Report No. 91-122, Marketing Science Institute, Cambridge, MA.
7. Aaker DA (1996) *Building Strong Brands*, The Free Press, New York, NY. Vol 3, No 2, pp 33-46.
8. Motameni R. and Shahorkhi M. (1998), "Brand Equity Valuation: A Global Perspective", *Journal of Product and Brand Management*, 7 (4), 275-290.
9. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Government". O'RQ-395, December 9, 2015, (Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015, No. 49, Article 611).
10. Resolution No. 728 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the procedure for providing electronic public services through the Unified Interactive State Services Portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated September 15, 2017.
11. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.
12. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.

13. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
14. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
15. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
16. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5.
17. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
18. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozиковich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
19. Azimovna M. S., Shohrukhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
20. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
21. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
22. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
23. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
24. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.
25. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
26. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 392-399.